

European Integration Processes for the Development of Future Foreign Language Specialists in the Information Society

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Summary

The article reveals and theoretically substantiates the trends of foreign language teachers' professional training in universities of Ukraine in terms of European integration, which are systematized in three areas: macro-level (system of education), meso-level (universities) and micro-level (subjects of educational process).

The article aims to substantiate the trends of foreign language teacher training in the context of European integration and the main directions of creative use of constructive ideas of European experience in the innovative development of education. The article lights up the system for improving foreign language teacher training in universities, which is based on updated goals, content and approaches to the implementation of basic concepts, principles and features of teacher training in European experience, enable us to improve the quality of teacher training, its competitiveness in the European labor market. In the article developed the conceptual model of strategic development of the university in the conditions of European integration.

It is emphasized that information technologies provide great opportunities for the development of professional skills and intellectual potential of future professionals. At present, the computerization of the educational process in higher education institutions is considered as one of the first and most promising areas for improving the quality of education. The article offered directions of internationalization of educational activity of university in the conditions of European integration. Diagnostic tools for the development of the university in terms of integration into the European educational space, individual rating and ranking of structural units of the university have been developed; main directions of activity of the laboratory of the skill of the teacher of higher school and methodical recommendations on the creation and the organization of work of scientific laboratories.

Key words:

information technologies, training, foreign language teacher, university, development strategy, globalization, European integration.

1. Introduction

Reforming the system of education in Ukraine depends on the research results, conducted by European and domestic scientists, related to the scientific and methodological justification of changes in the educational sphere. It is important to determine the theoretical and methodological foundations of the Europeanization of education and the development of a modern system of future teachers' professional training in universities in the context of European integration.

To enable European integration, the education system should focus on the core values of Western culture (parliamentarian, human rights, national minority rights, liberalization, freedom of movement, freedom of education at any level, lifelong learning, etc.). Therefore, the theory and practice of foreign language teacher training must be consistent with the theoretical and methodological principles of the organization of educational space in Europe. Any state needs the training of a new generation of foreign language teachers capable of implementing progressive ideas of domestic and foreign experience in educational practice. Therefore, the professional training of future teachers should be carried out in the context of integration into the European space, taking into account the achievements of pedagogical science of these countries.

Thus, given the particular severity and multifaceted problem of education in the European educational and scientific space, the validity of the main directions of reforming higher education, the problem of professional training of foreign language teachers in European integration requires systematic theoretical and methodological and methodological research.

The general purpose of continuous training is to prepare a practitioner, in particular a foreign language teacher, for professional activity in the context of informatization of society and mass global communication, able to use the whole arsenal of ICT tools to implement the main directions of informatization of education [17].

Information technology provides great opportunities for the development of professional skills and intellectual potential of future professionals. You need to make the most of these benefits [15].

At present, the computerization of the educational process in higher education institutions of Ukraine is considered as one of the first and most promising areas for improving the quality of education in higher education institutions. Great attention is paid to this problem, both at the level of ministries and at the level of higher education institutions themselves. However, full-scale computerization of the educational process in higher education institutions is a complex problem that requires long-term focused work and constant attention. [31].

Informatization and powerful technical equipment of the educational system significantly contribute to the humanization of education and the humanization of the educational process. Telecommunication systems, information service systems, reference and information systems, automated development and decision-making systems, modeling and simulation systems, training systems, etc. play an extremely important role in our life. [32].

An important role in the educational process of each person is the study of a foreign language with the help of information technology. The main purpose of learning a foreign language student is the formation of communicative competence, which means mastering the language as a means of intercultural communication, the development of skills to use it as a tool in the dialogue of cultures and civilizations in the modern world. This goal involves the achievement of learners, a level of communicative competence that would be sufficient for communication in oral (speaking, listening) and written (reading, writing) forms within certain communicative areas, the subject of situational speech and on the basis of the studied speech and speech material [27].

The educational purpose of learning a foreign language - the formation of positive personal qualities and character traits of learners, allows them to feel comfortable in a foreign language environment. Thus, in foreign language classes, the teacher must educate students, tolerance, openness, willingness to communicate, respect for the people whose language is studied and its culture, a positive attitude to a foreign language as an element of people's culture and a means of transmitting it to others, a sense of patriotism - love for their homeland, which is associated with awareness of their own national identity and willingness to represent their national culture in the dialogue of cultures, friendliness, politeness, attention and respect for the interlocutor as part of a culture of communication.

Education, upbringing and development of students in foreign language classes are provided by selecting educational material (texts for reading / listening, speech samples, visual aids, communication situations); organization of the educational process - setting problem tasks, using modern methods and techniques of teaching, creating an atmosphere in which learners would feel free to express their thoughts and feelings, views and assessments on the proposed topics of communication. The goals of teaching foreign languages are specified in the intermediate goals at all stages of the course, their specification also depends on the specifics of the educational institution. Computerization of the educational process helps to achieve these goals [25].

The developmental purpose of learning a foreign language involves the development and improvement of the following mental processes and abilities of learners: sense of language and style, etc.); mental processes associated with speech activity (the amount of long-term and working memory, attention, imagination, thinking operations; intellectual abilities of learners (ability to carry out problem-solving activities, transfer knowledge, skills, ability to translate from native language to a foreign language from one type of speech activity to another, from known (worked) situations of communication to new ones; ability to make analogies, classifications, generalizations); social abilities of learners, ie the ability and willingness of learners to communicate at the intercultural level (the ability to overcome feelings of fear and insecurity when meeting a stranger, unusual; the ability to see common features that unite all people, and specific national features, to be tolerant of the cultural values of other countries, to plan their speech actions independently); learning motivation of students through awareness of the relevance and prestige of learning a foreign language, the importance of learning, through positive emotions, various active teaching methods and techniques, the use of problematic issues and tasks, creating communicative situations, interesting learning material and its novelty, opportunity application of previously acquired knowledge, which helps the computerization of the educational process [25].

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for practical language acquisition for each individual, to choose such teaching methods that would allow each person to show their activity, their creativity and intensify the cognitive activity of students in the process of learning a foreign language [29] what is the professional position of a specialist in the implementation of English-language education with the help of computer technology in modern Ukrainian education.

In modern methods of teaching a foreign language, the learning situation is defined as a unit of learning content, as a way of organizing material for classes and as a criterion for organizing a system of exercises. In communicatively oriented foreign language learning, the stimulus for learning are situations, namely: the basis for the selection and organization of speech material, a condition for the formation of speech skills and the development of speech skills, which is

impossible without information support of the educational process [16].

For the effective foreign language education of learners and for the development of various human abilities by means of a foreign language, the needs of learners with different styles of perception should be taken into account: audials, verbals, visuals and kinesthetics. Therefore, the teacher is recommended to use a variety of learning strategies and learning styles that help each person realize their potential and express themselves [4].

2. Analysis of recent research and publications

Problems of European integration of higher education are analyzed in the works of scientists, which reveal the impact of the Spanish program of development of higher education teachers on approaches to learning. In the article by Burke and DeLeon, A. [6] report on the rethinking of the US education in the direction of quantitative assessment and qualitative learning outcomes of students. Lucas and Delgado-Algarra [20] in their treatises mount a portrait of a foreign language teacher of postmodern social sciences: a model of good practice in heritage education. Crişan [9] substantiates the challenges of postmodern society regarding higher education. Giner Gomis, Iglesias Martinez, and Lozano Cabezas [11] provide teaching of educational reality in preschool education in their reflections on the final project of teaching primary school children. Gómez et al. [12] reveal the conceptualization of the needs of renewal and professionalization of teaching in the educational environment. Lee and Chang [19] show the aspects of foreign language teacher training and the quality of learning in terms of student satisfaction. Claudio and Picazo [8] emphasize the importance of social reconstruction through the teaching and learning of the visual arts in teacher education. Annan [2] contributes to the training of competent foreign language teachers worldwide in the aspect of a paradigm shift for foreign language teacher education in Ghana. Brandenburg and Willcock [5] highlight the impact of the international component on public education through experimental design in preparation for learning. Zelenková and Hanesová [30] highlight the intercultural competence of university foreign language teachers as a challenge to internationalization. Filice and Bardetti [10] emphasize the importance of online education for TESOL teachers based on the results of the pilot project. Tomory [28] offers cooperative methods in terms of the development of social competence in the training of technical sciences teachers. Nguyen et al. [24] reveal the importance of the CDIO approach in developing a foreign language teacher training program to meet the requirements of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 in Vietnam. Mailool, et al. [21] offer foreign language teachers' experience in teaching moderate workload in the teacher education program (TPEP) in Indonesia. Mejía [22] shows functional diversity and inclusion in higher education institutions (IES) in Medellín (M.

Richaud, Ed.). Kic-Drgas [14] suggests the development of moderate exercise as part of the LSP course. He argues that the lack of foreign language knowledge for specific purposes and the increasing internationalization of domestic markets cause communication difficulties at the corporate level. Ineffective communication slows down decision-making processes and reduces the quality of services offered. In this regard, the moderate workload is becoming increasingly important in the professional environment. Given the need to ensure a high level of the foreign language, even at the interview level, the idea of teaching LSP with a moderate workload can fill the existing gap in employee training and increase employees' chances of success in the international environment. In his article, the author presents the results of a survey conducted among teachers of LSP in Poland. Agrusti, Poce, and Re [1] implement the Mooc-design system in the development of moderate workload and work skills in students of higher educational institutions.

Scientists compare the achievements of national and European education, analyze international standards of higher education, study the quality of Ukrainian education in the context of modern civilization, identify major trends in education in the European Union and areas of modernization of education in the context of XXI century.

The article aims to substantiate the trends of foreign language teacher training in the context of European integration and the main directions of creative use of constructive ideas of European experience in the innovative development of education.

The research hypothesis is based on the assumption that the effectiveness of the developed strategy and system for improving foreign language teacher training in universities in the context of European integration, which is based on updated goals, content and approaches to the implementation of basic concepts, principles and features of foreign language teacher training in European experience, enable us to improve the quality of foreign language teacher training, its competitiveness in the European labor market. The main objectives of the study, taking into account the identified trends, positive and constructive ideas of the European Union is to determine the prospects for the development of foreign language teacher training in universities in the context of globalization and European integration processes.

3. Research methods

3.1. Participants in the experiment

The experimental base of the study was Vinnytsia State Mykhailo Kotsyubynsky Pedagogical University, Drahomanov National Pedagogical University, Drohobych State Ivan Franko Pedagogical University, K. Ushinsky South Ukrainian National Pedagogical University, Central Ukrainian State Volodymyr Vynnychenko Pedagogical University, Kharkiv National Skovoroda Pedagogical University, Ternopil

National Volodymyr Hnatiuk Pedagogical University, where the general sample was made up of teachers, whose potential features revealed the peculiarities of foreign language teacher training in modern conditions and the main directions of creative use of constructive ideas of European experience in innovative development of education.

The experimental study involved 434 people, according to which seven study groups were staffed. The age of the participants of the experiment is 22 - 55 years. All the participants before the study were informed about the conditions for participation in the experiment and agreed to participate. The experiment was conducted by the decision of the specialized academic council of Vinnytsia State Mykhailo Kotsyubynsky Pedagogical University (protocol № 12 of February 17, 2012). The ethical rights of all participants are respected. The study was conducted in the natural conditions of the educational process of the Higher educational establishments, providing general conditions for participation in the experiment: the same time and duration of the training, the same measuring materials to diagnose the level of foreign language teacher training and the main directions of creative use of constructive ideas of European experience.

3.2. Methods of conducting a pedagogical experiment

Checking the effectiveness of the system of improving the professional training of foreign language teachers in universities of Ukraine in terms of European integration was carried out in 2012-2019 during four stages: theoretical and conceptual (2012-2013), analytical and exploratory (2014-2015), Organizational and formative (2015-2018), generalizing (2018-2019).

The program of research and experimental work included theoretical and methodological analysis; definition of stages, tasks and the program of research; definition of research methods; conducting longitudinal and comparative experiments and interpretation of their results by methods of mathematical statistics in order to determine the effectiveness of implementation in the training of future teachers of the conceptual model and system of improving foreign language teacher training in universities in terms of European integration, a generalization of research results to assess its effectiveness and prospects development of foreign language teacher training in universities in the context of globalization processes. The study of the peculiarities of the development and higher pedagogical education reforms in Great Britain, Finland, Germany, France, Denmark, Norway, Ireland, Poland, Italy, etc., carried out on the basis of 78 documentary original sources, gave grounds to conclude that for European countries quality education is determined by the relationship between theory, practice and research in order to strengthen the practical component of training through the development of practice-oriented routes; increasing requirements for personal,

educational, professional achievements and abilities of entrants; creation of a multi-stage system of selection and admission of candidates for training; expanding the powers of different types of schools in the process of foreign language teacher training and employment, preservation of their culture, language and national identity. In all European countries, there is an international unification of national educational standards, diversification of educational models, improvement of learning technologies. At the same time, each country seeks to enrich its historically developed educational potential by actively studying the innovative experience of the organization and content of education in other countries. This helps to determine the general patterns of development of education, to avoid mistakes caused by one-sidedness and hasty borrowing of foreign experience, serves to form an open educational space.

Based on the study of international experience in reforming higher education, we can conclude that these processes affect not only the qualifications of individual foreign language teachers but also the qualifications of higher education institutions.

One of the priority directions of the program of modernization of secondary and higher school is recognized as distance learning. In modern conditions, there is a need for higher education at a distance, which is caused by the need to study full-time, educated by people with disabilities and those who are abroad or in prison. This opportunity is provided by distance learning, which is carried out through information and educational technologies and communication systems, especially for effective foreign language education.

Distance learning in world practice is one of the established forms of learning. The pandemic has led to significant changes in the field of education around the world, it has caused educational problems in Ukraine. At the beginning of the quarantine in the spring of 2020, all educational institutions in the emergency mode switched to distance learning. It is in demand by society, it is popular. Distance learning is the most democratic form of education that allows educating the general public. Distance learning methods are used in higher education institutions, in school education, in the system of teacher training, in the system of management training.

The prospect and improvement of the distance learning system in Ukraine is the introduction of computer and audio-visual equipment in the educational process. Currently, the problem of distance education is being developed by all higher education institutions in Ukraine.

In the long run, e-learning will make learning not a boring and carefully planned commitment, but an exciting cognitive process in which the student himself participates. Learning everywhere, always and all your life with pleasure is about the slogan of the idea of distance education.

The methodological basis for working on distance learning requires maximum involvement of students, future teachers of foreign languages, in active learning, which increases their motivation to carry out training by distance

learning; speed of feedback, constant presence of the teacher, systematic consultations, creation of a special forum for communication between the teacher and students; great interaction between students and students and the teacher, which contributes to the satisfaction of students from learning. The effectiveness of pedagogical support in the process of distance learning is achieved by the following conditions: the presence of students' computer literacy, accounting for psychological patterns of perception, memory, attention and age of students, their individual and personal characteristics, creating psychological comfort, including the ability of the teacher to dialogue by means of information technologies, to find individual approach to students, realization of specially organized self-control of students and systematic control of the teacher on generalization of the knowledge provided at development of the corresponding curricula on teaching of a foreign language, possession of skills of independent work.

Each country needs to build its capacity to provide blended learning models. All educational institutions should be better prepared (if necessary) for the transition: from full-time to distance learning. This will protect education and create opportunities for more individualized approaches to teaching and learning, not only during future pandemics, but also during other shocks, such as natural disasters, which is possible when developing flexible curricula that can be taught in person or online. In addition, all educators, including foreign language teachers, must be well prepared to manage a wide range of IT devices and guide the reform of the education sector in line with the standards of the European Education Area. This is a long-term process and Ukraine is working in this direction. Authorities are developing distance education rules, making greater use of blended learning approaches, and working to increase the number of educational institutions with Internet connections and access to digital devices and equipment. Such focused work will help educational institutions not only to overcome the effects of COVID-19, but also to introduce more sustainable and flexible approaches in future educational activities aimed at maintaining continuity of learning and operational sustainability in higher education, through measures to expand the digitalization of the sector [18].

Intensive use of information and communication technologies in the life of modern society has led to a rethinking of the content of education and training of future foreign language specialists: the main role is played not so much by the information itself as the ability to work with it, critically comprehend and produce new knowledge; the main thing is not the amount of information, but its quality; information is needed for further practical application and transformation into knowledge, and the ability to work with information becomes one of the important competencies of the modern specialist in the new transformation of society: from information to the knowledge society. In this context, one of the main forms of training is distance learning, which is able to respond to the challenges of society [23].

The role of the teacher also changes significantly in this educational process. It is entrusted with such functions as coordinating the cognitive process, adjusting the course being studied, advising students in organizing an individual curriculum, managing their educational projects, and so on. It helps students in their professional self-determination. If we consider the features of distance education in terms of communication between a foreign language teacher and a student, we can identify the following characteristics:

self-education as a basis for distance learning, which involves the student's own motivation for their own learning, as well as a certain level of self-organization of the individual; communication between teacher and student on the principle of "to each other", which corresponds to the form and content of individual counseling;

communication and interaction "to each other" does not preclude the interaction of "one to many", because the teacher, in accordance with a pre-arranged schedule, works with many students. This form of interaction resembles traditional learning in classrooms;

interaction "many to many" means that it is possible to simultaneously communicate with many students who share experiences and impressions. Based on this, distance learning has a number of advantages over traditional learning: advanced educational technologies, availability of information sources, individualization of learning, convenient counseling system, democratic relations between student and teacher, convenient schedule and place of work.

The following measures have been implemented in Ukraine to support distance learning and learning. Primarily, support for distance learning and learning began with the broadcast of video lessons on television and the use of online distance learning platforms [18].

Substitute services - online courses - are gaining more and more strength. The popularity of such educational platforms as Coursera, edX and FutureLearn has noticeably increased. In 2020 alone [7] almost 32 million new users registered on these platforms, which is more than twice as many as in 2019 (14.3 million) [3].

The quantitative analysis confirms the popularity of open education: there are currently a large number of platforms that provide access to open educational resources from various fields of knowledge. Where the teacher, in particular, in a foreign language will be able to use new technologies in education.

The mass share of IT courses in open educational resources in relation to all offered is quite large: on the resource Intuit computer science courses occupy 70% of all courses, on Udemy - 43%, UoPeople - 28%, Edx - 24%.

Most of the courses are offered not only in programming and software development, although the relative weight of these courses is the largest (38.6% of the courses considered), but also in areas related to the study of specialized software in a particular scientific field, philology, mathematics, physics, biology, finance, etc.), with methods of processing various

information content, with cloud computing, etc. This suggests that modern youth has a variety of requests that are met by author courses from the world's leading teachers.

The analysis confirms the active development and implementation of open educational resources in the United States and EU countries. This explains most English-language projects. At the same time, there are platforms that are more focused on global distribution - Coursera and Udemy resources offer educational resources in different languages of the world (not only English) - 85% and 46.5%, respectively.

We can also talk about an extremely large number of courses on foreign open resources and too few of them in Ukraine. The development and promotion of open educational resources in Ukraine has begun, but we can not talk about the development of this movement. This is confirmed by the Ukrainian platforms Prometheus and VUM, which offer a small number of courses, and not only in the IT industry. In form they are similar to foreign educational resources. At the same time, we note that this content offers traditional video lectures with the usual methodological approaches to learning - this distinguishes Ukrainian educational resources from others [26].

As it is known, the processes of European integration have led to significant changes in the philosophy of education. The basis for substantiating the modern educational paradigm is the "philosophy of global problems", which covers a set of interrelated ideas and concepts based on the objectivity of the development of socio-cultural, political, economic, religious processes. The study of concepts of development of education in the European Union on the basis of the new philosophy of education allowed to substantiate the position that the set of modern worldview ideas and theories affects the definition of the basic laws of education; methodology of teaching and education; as well as strategies and tactics of scientific and practical activities.

The analysis of the results of scientific research and many years of experience of the author confirmed that the developed strategy of university development and its consistent implementation affects the positive dynamics of foreign language teacher training (methodological, organizational, semantic and methodological levels, as well as management). Along with this, insufficient attention was paid to solving the following problems: introduction of the latest scientific achievements in the content of subject foreign language teacher training; popularization and marketing of scientific achievements; strengthening scientific ties with foreign universities; expanding participation in international research projects, etc. Based on the analysis of strategic directions of development of universities in the conditions of integration into the European educational and scientific space, the directions of internationalization of the university are determined, taking into account Ukraine's orientation to integration into the European educational and scientific space. During the development of the conceptual model of strategic development of the university in the conditions of European

integration, we took into account the progressive and constructive ideas of the leading universities of Ukraine and the world; provisions of legislative acts and normative-legal documents regulating the activity of institutions of higher education; a level of competence and readiness of the scientific team for innovative processes and continuous professional development.

4. Results

To confirm the effectiveness of the system of improving foreign language teacher training in universities in the context of European integration, a longitudinal research method was chosen. The longitudinal method (from Latin 'long') - a long and systematic study of the same object. Such long-term tracking of the object (usually by a pre-arranged program) allows us to identify the dynamics of its operation and predict further development. In identifying the trends in foreign language teacher training and opportunities for their impact on the system of improving foreign language teacher training in universities in terms of European integration, the object of the longitudinal experiment is a set of key performance indicators of higher education institutions, which was influenced by the developed conceptual model of university development defined strategy. In recent years, university researchers have performed a number of contractual research work, which is funded by the state budget of Ukraine, Vinnytsia regional and city budgets, local budgets of district administrations, as well as foreign organizations.

We believe that the development and implementation of a conceptual model of university and the development strategy of the university in terms of integration into the European educational and scientific space gives a significant synergistic effect on socio-economic development at regional and national levels, including annually:

- the university prepares for itself on the average 5-6 doctors and 7-10 candidates of sciences, and also 2-3 doctors and 16-18 candidates of pedagogical sciences for other institutions of higher education of Ukraine;
- publication of monographs, textbooks and manuals by the staff of the Pedagogical University helps to expand the access of other scientists and citizens of the society to the results of research;
- systematic foreign internships of scientific and pedagogical staff of the university within the signed with more than 50 foreign institutions of higher education, research institutions and organizations promotes the study and implementation of the best European experience in Ukraine;
- methods of education of children with disabilities developed by university foreign language teachers contribute to the improvement of the centers of social rehabilitation of children with disabilities;

- projects on digitalization of the educational process used by the educational and methodical center of vocational education of Vinnytsia region.

The results of a longitudinal study of the effectiveness of the system of improving the professional training of teachers in universities of Ukraine in the context of European integration confirmed the increase in scientific performance of teachers and students.

We also note carrying out on the basis of Pedagogical University the All-Ukrainian student's Olympiad on programming, the Second round of the All-Ukrainian competition of student's research works on "Primary education"; The second stage of the All-Ukrainian Student Olympiad in the discipline "Ukrainian language (for professional purposes)"; Taras Shevchenko International Language and Literature Competition and regional stages of the Petro Jacyk International Ukrainian Language Competition. In total, in all international student scientific Olympiads, competitions, tournaments, championships in 2019 won 96 prizes, which is 35% higher than the previous year (Fig. 5). The winners of these competitions usually enter graduate school, which determines the appropriate dynamics in the training of scientific and pedagogical staff in the field (Fig. 6). Thus, the results of a longitudinal study conducted over five years show a significant positive trend in the main indicators of the scientific and professional activity of foreign language teachers, departments and faculties, which significantly affected the quality of foreign language teacher training in the European integration process.

Fig. 5. The total number of prizes in all scientific competitions, contests, tournaments, championships in 2014-2019

Fig. 6. Dynamics of the number of entrants to the graduate school of VSPU

The value of the results obtained in the process of implementation and testing of the system of improving the professional training of foreign language teachers in universities of Ukraine in the context of European integration led to the following social effects:

- The project "Inclusive educational space and innovative technologies in education" with the support of Vinnytsia city public organization of social formation and development of certain vulnerable categories of youth "Parostok" helps to spread volunteer practice and form a positive image of a foreign language teacher's assistant in Vinnytsia region;
- developed scientific-methodical system of professional training of future specialists by means of modern information and communication technologies, which combines target, methodological, content, organizational-activity, diagnostic-comparative components, improves the quality of students' training and provides a sufficient level of development of their information competence;
- psychological and pedagogical training developed by the staff of the Pedagogical University is widely used in the education of children with special needs; contribute to the organization of a psychologically comfortable environment and the formation of values in life;
- psycho-correctional techniques in art therapy help reduce the risk of conflict, create a positive microclimate for the development of children with disabilities and improve psycho-physical, psycho-emotional well-being in the world of children in this category;
- organized work on psychological assistance aimed at solving psychological and overcoming social problems by participants in hostilities;
- psychological training, commissioned by the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine for the new police and the court, help to improve the level of communication and work with people with disabilities;
- study of the species structure and distribution of animals and plants in the Vinnytsia region helps to increase the efficiency of environmental work;
- work on the preparation of scientific substantiations of the need to create protected objects in the region: botanical, ornithological, herpetological and general zoological reserves, regional and national nature parks contributes to the creation of an integrated system of protected areas of Vinnytsia as a structural component of the National and global ecological network;
- studying the effectiveness of the latest programs in physical education provides improved physical and functional fitness of people of all ages, as well as helps to explore the impact of physical activity of different directions on the mental and physical performance of students;
- study of the impact of physical activity in the anaerobic lactate mode of energy supply in combination with the method of "endogenous-hypoxic respiration" contributes to the physical and functional fitness of athletes-swimmers;
- development of effective programs on physical education provides improvement of physical health of the population of the Podolsk region and introduction of a model of a healthy way of life of student's youth in the educational process of higher educational institutions of Ukraine;

- determination of physiological mechanisms of influence of different types of physical activity on the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, as well as on the typological properties of higher nervous activity of pupils and students;
- the program of designing of ecological and economic business allows to form the subjects of business activity such psychological components, as the value of natural environment and motivation of preservation, support and development of an environment of own existence; due to the program of ecological and professional development of business entities, the current norms and stereotypes of economic activity have been significantly changed due to environmental friendliness;
- the method of determining the psychological mechanisms of formation of addictive behavior helps to determine the specifics of addictive behavior in people with neurotic disorders due to the use of psychoactive substances;
- research of archival documents and journalistic investigations (eyewitness interviews) make it possible to find out previously unknown facts about the criminal activities of the Nazis in the Vinnytsia region;
- the proposed legal basis for information support of higher education institutions contributes to the improvement of current legislation and the development of new regulations governing the information support of higher education institutions.

The results of the study confirmed that the system of improving the professional training of foreign language teachers in universities in the context of European integration is dynamic, purposeful, intensive and productive. This is due to the professional requirements for Ukrainian foreign language teachers in the context of European integration processes; the influence of the value-semantic potential of globalization and European integration processes on the modernization of education in Ukraine and are determined by the peculiarities of the integration of education of Ukraine into the European space. Thus, it is proved that for a foreign language teacher who will work in the conditions of European integration, several new requirements will be put forward, and therefore the model of his personality will be complicated. Given the dynamic changes in the modern education system under the influence of integration processes, it is necessary to build a dynamic model of a new foreign language teacher for a united Europe. Such a model cannot be static for a long period of time, as it must take into account the changes taking place in society.

Experimental verification of the system of improving foreign language teacher training in universities in the context of European integration was carried out at different stages of longitudinal research, the results of which indicate a noticeable positive dynamics of key indicators of the scientific and professional activity of participants in the educational process. In 2017-2019, the University took first place among universities according to the results of the All-Ukrainian competition of student research papers in natural, technical and human sciences and second place among universities according to the results of the All-Ukrainian Student Olympiad

in scientific disciplines and specialties. In total, in all international and all-Ukrainian student scientific Olympiads, competitions, tournaments, championships in 2019 we won 99 prizes, which is 38% higher than the previous year.

The analysis of the dynamics of the university's rating indicators in 2019 to confirm the effectiveness of the system of improving foreign language teacher training in terms of European integration showed that it took the fourth place among universities.

The study of the results of research and experimental work has confirmed that the scientific and pedagogical community of Ukraine is taking significant steps to ensure a proper place in the global educational environment. Constructive ideas of the European experience are expediently correlated with the Ukrainian realities. This allows us to determine the system of priorities in terms of integration of education in Ukraine in the European educational space. Most universities are looking for ways to solve the problem of improving the quality of education in accordance with the requirements of European standards. The positive dynamics of improving the quality of foreign language teacher training has become possible due to the introduction of a system of improving foreign language teacher training in universities of Ukraine in the context of European integration. It is an integral part of the strategy for the development of a university on the way to the European educational and scientific space and at the same time an important component of the conceptual model.

5. Discussion of results

Ukraine's integration into the European scientific and educational space objectively requires the creation of an optimal balance between internal and external academic mobility, import and export of educational services. Since the common European space, on the one hand, promotes the growth of student mobility and teaching staff, and on the other - academic mobility is a necessary condition for the formation of a common educational space. The conceptual foundations of academic mobility in the European research and education space are based on the fact that studying abroad can become an integral part of university education.

In the process of integration of Ukrainian universities into the European educational space, the academic mobility of students and teachers plays an important role, which contributes to the formation of a qualitatively new generation of teachers capable of occupying a worthy place in the world labor market; improving the availability, quality and efficiency of education; ensuring the mobility of human capital for the formation of global educational space. It should be noted that the mobility of the administrative and teaching staff of higher education institutions contributes to raising the level of the national educational system based on the study of foreign experience and prevents the lag of domestic university education due to insufficient funding.

González-Geraldo, Monroy, and Igea [13] argue that the process of globalization coincides in time with a fundamental transition to the information society, i.e. to a new global community based on information. A necessary condition for improving the quality of education is the use of information and communication technologies in the educational process.

One of the main trends in foreign language teacher training in the context of European integration is to expand education for all, create an inclusive environment, universal design and "smart" adaptation to appropriate conditions for education for all categories of students, including people with disabilities, as well as training future foreign language teachers to work with children with special educational needs. In order to prepare future foreign language teachers for the psychological and support of children with special educational needs, the "Center for Author's Methods and Modern Practices" has been established, which is a place of social integration of students, teachers, children and parents. It is a holistic educational platform for children and adults with different starting positions and needs and features in learning.

One of the national priorities of Ukraine is the objective need to present the science of the state in the global scientific and information space and increase the level of its influence in the world. We emphasize the need to shift the focus in the functioning of the library as one of the infrastructural information and communication components of the university and increase the role of higher education libraries in the development of institutional missions and goals in terms of the postmodern approach.

6. Conclusions

Therefore, the article is justified substantiate the trends of teacher training in the context of European integration and the main directions of creative use of constructive ideas of European experience in the innovative development of education.

In the research disclosed the effectiveness of the developed strategy and system for improving teacher training in universities in the context of European integration, which is based on updated goals, content and approaches to the implementation of basic concepts, principles and features of teacher training in European experience, enable us to improve the quality of teacher training, its competitiveness in the European labor market.

Based on the analysis of strategic directions of development of universities in the conditions of integration into the European educational and scientific space the essence of internationalization of educational activity of university in the conditions of European integration is substantiated. Internationalization of the university involves the expansion of academic mobility programs; training of future foreign language teachers who have the necessary competencies for life and successful professional activity in a multicultural

multilingual environment; mobility of educational programs and institutional partnership; strengthening the role of the university as a scientific, educational, cultural and socio-educational center of the region; introduction into the educational process and scientific activity of the information educational and SMART environment. Internationalization at the university level involves the introduction of the international aspect of university management in order to improve the quality of teaching and research and achieve a high level of professional training of future teachers; modernization and increasing the competitiveness of educational programs and research; development of international cooperation based on the expansion of academic exchange programs and participation in international projects; international accreditation of educational programs in order to internationalize training. External internationalization of the university is provided by diversification, wider involvement of foreign students in Ukrainian universities; introduction of educational programs of international dimension and European educational standards.

It is proved that the multi-vector tasks of development of universities take into account the main trends of professional education in the European Union, and the strategic development plan in the context of European integration is based on three system-forming components: mission (organization of universities based on personality-oriented paradigm and new methodology for the development of modern education, which is a synthesis of civilizational, cultural, personal, activity, dialogic, competence, praxeological, communicative, integration and information methodological approaches), vision (creating a favorable environment for personal development; ensuring the quality of education according to European standards; SMART space, development of scientific potential of universities, integration into the international and scientific space, development of corporate culture and leadership as a modern university management system sites; promoting the development of student government; creation on the basis of universities of centers of inclusive, non-formal and informal education) and values (national consciousness, respect for the individual, honesty, trust, mutual assistance, friendliness, tolerance, responsibility, active citizenship, initiative, creativity, academic integrity, openness, innovation, continuous self-improvement) of participants in the educational process.

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